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Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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reduce labor market tensions, and alleviate poverty, the Concept of the Socio-Economic Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was approved on 2021-12-03. This Concept places special emphasis on improving living standards and reducing poverty, refining the regulatory framework for poverty assessment and reduction, creating labor-intensive jobs, supporting poor and vulnerable groups and strengthening their capital, enhancing the targeting and effectiveness of the social protection system, and improving the quality of social protection services [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Although scholars have proposed various definitions of poverty, the concept has not yet been fully and unambiguously articulated. Some economists define poverty as the inability to meet basic human needs, whereas others interpret it as a restriction of individual freedom of choice or as the persistent presence of social, educational, and health barriers that limit a person's participation in socio-economic life [2].

In general, in international practice, poverty is understood as a condition that reflects insufficient resources for individuals or social groups to secure minimum subsistence, maintain work capacity, and ensure generational continuity [3].

In Uzbekistan, a number of researchers have addressed this issue. For instance, Qalandar Abdurahmanov, in his textbook *Economics of Labor*, defines poverty as the level of consumption that merely preserves working capacity and represents the lower bound of resource reproduction for labor [4]. In our view, poverty is an indicator that reflects both the quality of life and the standard of living of society's members and is characterized by a minimal level of satisfaction of essential living needs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Based on the study of this topic, mathematical and statistical analysis methods were employed to examine key indicators such as the standard of living and the level of poverty in the country, and to derive well-grounded conclusions regarding the overall socio-economic situation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In his address to the Parliament on 2020-01-24, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, for the first time publicly emphasized the existence of a poor segment of the population, noting that 12–15 percent of the country's population—approximately 4.5–5 million people—live in poverty. He also identified as a key priority the implementation of practical measures to address this problem, including the development of targeted policies to raise incomes, improve living standards and quality of life, and establish a system of indicators that accurately reflects poverty levels [5].

The main indirect and direct factors contributing to impoverishment can be summarized as follows:

1. In predominantly rural areas, insufficient knowledge and skills among the population reduce their competitiveness in the labor market;
2. Weak outcomes in the education system and low quality of healthcare services in the regions;
3. A high prevalence of paternalistic attitudes in certain social groups and excessive expenditures associated with traditional practices;
4. High unemployment in some regions, insufficient job creation, low incomes, and a generally low standard of living.

Conversely, when production expands, human capital (knowledge and skills) improves, employment rises, and labor market competitiveness increases, material well-being tends to grow accordingly.

According to the World Bank, relatively high poverty rates in Uzbekistan are observed in the Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, and Andijan regions, as well as in the Republic of Karakalpakstan [6]. Calculations indicate that the daily income of individuals classified as poor ranges from USD 1.0 to USD 1.2, which is directly related to minimum consumption expenditures [7]. At the global level, the minimum standard of living remains a key benchmark and is continuously monitored.

Several thresholds are used to assess poverty and to define a decent standard of living. If an individual's income (or expenditures) falls below the specified benchmark, that person is considered poor:

1. The poverty line is determined by evaluating expenditures or income required to purchase a minimum daily food basket and essential non-food items, as well as the household's capacity to consume a defined set of goods and services. For example, according to the methodology of the State Statistics Committee, individuals in Uzbekistan who consume (or spend) less than 2,100 kcal per day are classified as poor [7].

2. By 2019-12-31, Uzbekistan's GDP per capita amounted to USD 1,723, which served as the basis for classifying the country as a lower-middle-income economy under the World Bank's classification [8].

3. According to a report published by the Ministry of Finance for 2020-04–2020-05, approximately 1.772 million citizens (about 42.6 percent) earned wages subject to personal income tax of up to USD 100 per month, while 1.066 million people earned between USD 100 and USD 200 per month [9].

4. According to the Center for Economic Research and Reforms, compared with the national average, poor households are 12 times less likely to own a personal computer, 11 times less likely to own a private car, 8 times less likely to own an air conditioner, 4 times less likely to own a vacuum cleaner, 4 times less likely to own a washing machine, 2 times less likely to own a refrigerator, and 1.5 times less likely to own a television set and mobile communication devices [10].

The poor segment of the population is not only unable to benefit fully from the country's rapid economic growth, but also faces limited opportunities to contribute to development due to restricted participation in various spheres of society. In this context, the state provides free secondary education, guarantees a basic package of medical services, offers specialized assistance for socially significant and high-risk conditions, and extends benefits to low-income households.

At present, only the first two methods are applied to measure poverty in Uzbekistan. According to the approach based on minimum consumption expenditures, the poverty rate is 11.4% [11]. Using the income-based approach, poverty amounts to 36.6% when the threshold is USD 5.5 per day, and 9.6% when the threshold is USD 3.6 per day [12].

In recent years, substantial progress has been achieved in establishing publicly accessible databases for poverty research. These resources make it possible to test multiple hypotheses regarding the characterization of poverty, its underlying causes, and the effects of specific programs and policy reforms on poverty outcomes.

Based on the determinants of poverty, its distribution can be classified into several groups.

1) Rural households primarily dependent on agricultural activities. The following features are typical for these households [15]:

- a relatively high share of hired employment and a stable ratio between employed and unemployed family members (approximately 1:1.5);
- a low level of vocational education among older family members;
- low productivity of available land due to water scarcity and limited land quality;
- larger household size and a higher dependency burden on employed members. For these households, a key vulnerability is the low and volatile income that depends on agricultural market conditions and exogenous factors affecting farming activities.

2) Households in small towns, urban-type settlements, and district centers, largely consisting of employees in non-agricultural enterprises. Their main characteristics include:

- food consumption close to the national average;
- a relatively moderate dependency burden on employed members;
- a comparatively higher educational attainment of the household head;
- a low employment rate among able-bodied household members;
- limited or no access to land and small household size. The principal risks for these households include increases in consumer prices, delays in wage payments, and a deterioration in the financial performance of non-agricultural enterprises.

3) Urban households, which are characterized by:

- relatively small household size;
- a significant dependency burden due to school-age children and elderly non-working members;
- incomplete family structures, including the absence of one breadwinner;
- employment of able-bodied members predominantly in budget-funded sectors;
- limited or no access to land.
- For these households, the main risk factors include rising consumer prices, health shocks affecting working-age members, and job loss.

4) Mixed rural and urban households with the following features [15]:

- low levels of vocational education among able-bodied members and limited demand for their skills in the labor market;
- unstable and low-skilled employment (including unskilled workers across sectors, temporary and seasonal workers, and entrepreneurs operating in the informal sector);
- limited access to land or low land productivity.

The relative size and spatial concentration of poor households depend on the type of settlement and the condition of production infrastructure. Several locations where poverty tends to concentrate can be identified [15]:

- rural areas distant from transport corridors and industrial agglomerations;
- multi-sector small cities experiencing production stagnation;

- district centers located outside major transport–industrial agglomerations.

For a large share of the population, overcoming poverty requires coordinated public support, as some groups face an elevated risk of social exclusion. At the same time, market mechanisms create opportunities for upward mobility, which underscores the importance of inclusive policies that broaden access to such opportunities.

Poverty reduction can be advanced by adhering to key public policy principles, including the expansion of access to decent and fairly paid employment and the encouragement of able-bodied citizens to engage in sustainable self-employment.

Efforts to combat and prevent poverty may be implemented along several complementary directions:

- economic measures aimed at raising the living standards of individuals and the population as a whole (income growth, employment policies, investment, taxation, and targeted social assistance);
- risk protection measures to enhance the effectiveness of systems that protect the population against major life risks (loss of work capacity, illness, disability, unemployment, old age, death, and loss of a breadwinner);
- improvements in social assistance systems, including both material and non-material support, free meals, assistance in restoring the rights of persons with disabilities, home-based and day-care social services, and the provision of social housing.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Anti-poverty recommendations should be grounded in the characteristics of low-income households, the socio-economic barriers that limit their participation in community life, and the most promising development pathways, as well as in coherent policy actions at both the macroeconomic and microeconomic levels, since together these elements determine the effectiveness and sustainability of poverty-reduction efforts. Today, a substantial share of the world's disadvantaged population continues to face unmet needs in key areas such as energy access, water supply, sanitation, and information technologies, while at the same time the attractiveness of market segments that serve low-income groups is increasing, particularly under conditions of slower growth in advanced economies. As an economically active segment of society, low-income groups can contribute to economic growth as workers and entrepreneurs if their access to productive opportunities is expanded; consequently, addressing gaps in knowledge and skills and investing in education and training for the poor represent critical drivers of inclusive development. Inclusive business models should therefore be adapted to market environments where institutions, infrastructure, and education levels remain relatively limited; in such contexts, products and services need to be affordable, accessible, and effectively promoted, and are typically characterized by low unit margins combined with high sales volumes, which implies not only the provision of low-cost goods but also the creation of value propositions that directly address the unmet needs of low-income consumers. Against this background, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan can play a coordinating role in reducing barriers to inclusive business, including regulatory inefficiencies or gaps, administrative burdens, insufficient rural infrastructure and transport connectivity, and skills constraints, making the strengthening of structured dialogue between public authorities and business representatives particularly important. It is recommended that the Chamber periodically organize training programs focused on promoting investment opportunities in inclusive business, identifying underserved markets, and examining the specific features of inclusive business models, as well as organize annual product fairs for enterprises engaged in inclusive business, where entrepreneurs can exchange experience and establish partnerships; in addition, launching an annual “Best Inclusive Business Model” competition, publicizing its results and exemplary projects, and introducing a dedicated nomination such as “Best Inclusive Business Project of the Year” within existing award frameworks can serve as effective incentive mechanisms. Poverty reduction and prevention should be pursued through a combination of economic measures aimed at raising living standards, including income growth, employment policies, investment, taxation, and targeted social assistance, through risk-protection measures that enhance the effectiveness of systems safeguarding the population against major life risks such as loss of work capacity, illness, disability, unemployment, old age, death, and loss of a breadwinner, and through continuous improvement of social assistance systems, encompassing both material and non-material support, free meals, assistance in restoring the rights of persons with disabilities, the provision of home-based and day-care social services, and access to social housing. Finally, international experience suggests that broad income redistribution through generalized transfers alone is not a sufficiently effective instrument for sustainable poverty reduction; in many developed countries, policy has shifted toward approaches that strengthen incentives to work and invest in human capital, and therefore well-designed support measures should be combined with active labor market policies, skills development, and entrepreneurship support to foster self-reliance and long-term inclusion while preserving adequate social protection for those in need.

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